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A Bi-Annual, Open Access Peer Reviewed International Journal
Volume 03, Issue 01, March 2026

Factors influencing consumers' perception towards online shopping in rural areas of Bulandshahr

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Received: 20 March 2026 Accepted & Reviewed: 25 March 2026, Published: 31 March 2026

Abstract

Online shopping is emerging as a new approach of shopping in rural part of India, driven by the increasing utilisation of the internet among the younger rural population. The young generation finds it more convenient compared to traditional shopping. This study explores the various factors influencing rural consumers' perception of online shopping. The purpose of this research is to identify the pros and cons of online shopping, that shapes rural buying behaviour in this digital era. These findings offer insights for the market, policymakers, and e-commerce companies for making their policies and strategies for the rural market. Bulandshahr district in the state of Uttar Pradesh was selected as the geographical area for the present study. A study was conducted among 150 respondents by using purposive sampling.

Keywords: e-commerce, rural people, consumers' perception, traditional shopping

Introduction

Online shopping has experienced significant growth in value over recent years due to its convenience, variety, and ease of comparing prices. Online shopping, it can be described as the process of purchasing and selling goods and services over the internet. In India, it has gained popularity following the arrival of numerous websites, including Amazon, Flipkart, and others. Historically, online shopping began with the exchange of data through the internet. In 1960, IBM developed online transaction processing (OLTP), and Michael Aldrich launched the electronic shopping company CompuServe in 1969. In 1995, online shopping changed the Shopping pattern in India with the arrival of new websites like Amazon and eBay.

The era of e-shopping has taken a new turn at present in India. Customers can now have the luxury of shopping due to the availability of cheap internet rates and the development of various mobile applications. Currently, there are 5.56 million active internet users across the world, which is approximately two-thirds of the global population. The Indian market was significantly affected in 2020 due to an increase in internet penetration, and this trend continues afterward. India has a population of 954.40 million active internet users, and it is rising continuously. The increase in the number of internet user in rural areas of India has been growing significantly in recent years. As of March 2024, there were 398.35 million internet subscribers from rural part of india out of a total of 954.40 million internet subscribers in India. Several factors are contributing to this growth, like the Digital India program and the Bharat Net project, which the government runs. Additionally, the increase in the number of active mobile phone users and the affordable data plan have a positive impact on it.

Literature review:

Hamsa E (2025) - This study found that Flipkart is most popular among rural people, and they prefer the cash-on-delivery method for payments.

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S. Sanketh(2024)- A research is based on the various parameters, such as technology, trust, payment system, delivery service, etc, that are influencing the rural people. Most people consider technology to be a big problem in rural India.

Deshel Leviness Fernandes, V. Shailashree (2023) - This study reveals that young consumer exhibit a high level of comfort with online purchasing are comfortable making purchases online because of high quality, lower prices, and convenience etc. Most people show a preference for buying books and electronics gadgets through online platform.

Koppala Venugopal et al. (2021). This study reveals that technical education is a challenging aspect for the rural people of India, and they found that the lack of network connectivity is a problem in these areas.

Priyanka A Deshmukh, Shweta Chourasia (2020)-This study reveals that respondents have a favourable attitude for online shopping. Flipkart and Amazon are the most preferred platform among customers. This study also reveals that the additional or hidden charges quoted by the shopping sites are a common problem faced by rural and urban consumers.

A study by Ajay Kumar (2018) studying the effect of internet accessibility on rural population and there behaviour towards online shopping shows that online shopping is becoming popular in rural areas where high-speed internet connection is available.

Ashishkumar Bhatt (2014). This research found that online shopping is very popular and comfortable among Indian people because of multiple variables, such as COD, customization of products, door-step delivery, etc.

Mc Hugh, Eoghan Ciaran (2014). This study found that online shopping is independent of the buyer's geographical location.

Research methodology:

This study focuses on “the factors influencing consumer perception towards online shopping in rural areas of Bulandshahr”. This research is being conducted among 100 respondents by using purposive sampling. Self-structured questionnaires were created and distributed among respondents. A pie chart is used for arranging the data, and the hypothesis was examined by using a chi-square test.

Objectives of the study:

- 1.1 To study the users' reviews and ratings to decide their purchase.
- 1.2 To study the most preferred website for online shopping by rural people.
- 1.3 To study the market share shift from traditional retail to e-commerce.
- 1.4 To study consumer satisfaction with the delivery and shipping services provided by e-commerce.

Hypothesis:

- 2.1 H0: Gender and consumer perception for shifting from traditional to E-commerce has no significant correlation.
- 2.2 H0: Age and consumer perception toward the delivery and shipping service provided by E-commerce has no significant correlation.

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After collecting the responses, the data were systematically classified, tabulated, and analysed. The questionnaire consisted close ended questions to measure respondents' perception towards this topic "Factors influencing consumers' perception towards online shopping in rural areas of Bulandshahr" the collected data was tabulated for analyse and to examine the association between variable, the chi-square test was applied, hypothesis testing was conducted using 5% significance level to decide for the rejection and acceptance of null hypothesis. A detailed analysis of each question included in the questionnaire is given below :

Analysis of Questionnaire

Age of the respondents:

The Pie Chart shows an interesting correlation between age and the acceptance of e-commerce platforms for purchasing goods. It displays the acceptance of e-commerce along the age-specific segment of the population. The Yellow area of the diagram shows that almost fifteen percent of those who choose e-commerce for buying are above thirty-five years old. The red area of the diagram indicates that respondents are slightly higher than thirty percent who use e-commerce platforms for purchasing activities. The remaining respondents, who make up half of the total, are under twenty-five years old.

Gender of the respondents:

Gender-wise adoption of e-commerce for purchasing reveals some compelling findings that men no longer have a lead over women in adopting e-commerce. Their share in e-commerce participation in purchasing goods and services online is more than that of men.

Occupation of the respondents:

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Occupation
 100 responses

Occupation-wise data indicate that housewife respondents make significant purchases through e-commerce. Their total share stands at thirty-six percent in overall purchases using e-commerce. Farmers and self-employed contributions in online purchases show a similar trend; More than twenty-five respondents who make online purchases are students.

Income of the respondents:

Income annually
 100 responses

The income variable gives an intriguing picture of the use of e-commerce for the purchasing experience. Less than twenty percent of respondents whose income is above five lakhs use e-commerce for purchasing goods. Approximately seventeen percent of respondents whose income is in the range of two to five lakh use e-commerce. The below two lakh income group does the bulk of the purchases online.

How often do you make online purchase compared to traditional store purchase?
 100 responses

Share of respondents who are using both traditional and e-commerce platforms for purchase is in the majority. Data reveal that almost 50% of respondents purchase online. However, the percentage of people buying from traditional shares showed a significant decrease.

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To what extent ability to shop 24/7 influences your decision to buy online than traditional retail?
100 responses

A pie diagram shows consumer preference for buying online due to the timing of shopping hours. The majority of the respondents cited it as a factor for opting to shop online.

Is comparing prices online driving the shift towards E-Commerce shopping?
100 responses

A marked shift in consumer behaviour is observable when asked about their grounds for choosing E-commerce for availing of its service. A significant number of respondents give comparing prices of goods as a reason to move to E-commerce; however, 36% of the respondents effected by the comparison of prices.

1.1 To study the users' reviews and ratings to decide their purchase.

How important are users reviews and rating in deciding your purchase from online platforms?
100 responses

User reviews and ratings also play a factor in increasing the use of e-commerce platforms for shopping purposes. Almost half of the respondents replied affirmatively in deciding to buy online due to the favourable rating and review of shopping online.

1.2 To study the most preferred website for online shopping by rural people.

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Which website do you prefer most for online shopping?

100 responses

A significant number of consumers favoured buying from Amazon in rural areas, indicating its strong dominance, which is almost 34% of all respondents. However, Myntra follows 25%, showing a significant share; Meesho holds 21%, making it another major competitor. Overall, the finding highlights Amazon's leading position.

What factor will encourage you to consider shopping more in traditional retail stores?

100 responses

The answer to what encourages respondents to still buy from the store presents an intriguing situation. Approximately half of the respondents say exclusive promotion of goods is the reason behind their purchase, as more than a quarter of the respondents still favour in-store buying due to competitive pricing. Improved consumer service also plays a role in encouraging in-store shopping.

1.3 To study the market share shift from traditional retail to e-commerce.

What is the main reason for your shift from traditional to E-commerce ?

100 responses

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The major reason respondents cited for moving towards online purchase was the accessibility of a wide range of products. The second most important factor influencing them to purchase online was convenience. Only a marginal number of respondents moved to online purchase due to the heavy discount offered by the company.

H₀: Gender and consumer perception for shifting from traditional to E-commerce has no significant correlation.

Person	Convenience	Lower price	Wide range of products	Discount	Total
Male	14	13	10	4	41
Female	11	17	23	8	59
	25	30	33	12	100

Chi-square test :

Table value (3 d.f.), (5% level of significance) = 7.815

Calculated Value (χ^2) = 4.212

Hence,

the Result of the survey supports the hypothesis. So , we conclude that the gender and consumer perception for shifting from traditional to e-commerce has significant correlation.

Are you satisfied with the delivery and shipping service provided by E-Commerce?
100 responses

When asked about the level of satisfaction with the delivery and shipping experience of the e-commerce platform, more than half of the respondents gave a favourable answer. However, respondents' negative response to it was very low.

H₀: Age and consumer perception toward the delivery and shipping service provided by E-commerce has no significant correlation.

Gender	Yes	No	Total
Male	34	7	41
Female	48	11	59
	82	18	100

Chi-square test:

Table value (1 d.f.), (5% level of significance) = 3.841

Calculated Value (χ^2) = 0.0399

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Hence,

the result of survey supports hypothesis. So, we conclude that age and consumer perception toward the delivery and shipping service provided by E-commerce has significant correlation.

Conclusion:

This study revealed that e-commerce has a significant influence on consumer perception of online shopping in rural areas. The research, conducted among 100 respondents, found that several factors contribute to shaping consumer behaviour towards e-commerce, including a wide range of products, convenience, and home delivery services. It was also observed that online shopping sources impact consumer perception, with many households actively participating in this trend.

The study further highlighted that Amazon is the most popular e-commerce platform in rural areas. However, certain limitations exist, including challenges in generalization, as consumer behaviour is dynamic and keeps changing over time. Moreover, this study was limited to the Bulandshahr district of Uttar Pradesh, which may restrict its wider applicability.

Overall, this study offers valuable insights into rural consumers' perceptions of online shopping and provides a foundation for future research and strategic planning.

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